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“THREE MONTHS AND A MIRACLE”

It's twelve midnight, Peter's not home yet, Riley's beginning to worry. Where could her husband be? Suddenly, she noticed someone opening the back door. She sighed in relief seeing it was her husband, at last. She went to him and asked him where he went, only to find out that Peter's severely wasted with alcohol. She couldn't believe what she had witnessed. When did her husband ever learned to drink? She had so many questions but she knew she couldn't confront him in this state. So, she just helped him rest.

Morning came. Riley sat alone at the kitchen table, waiting for Peter to explain things to her, but when Peter came in to drink a glass of water, there were no words uttered. He just walked silently, passed her, as if Riley's invisible. This sudden change of behavior enraged Riley but she is just too smart to read between the lines. She said to herself, “Ahah! You want to play this game, huh? Fine, I'm sure I'll win. Let the games begin.”

A few weeks earlier, it was Peter and Riley's tenth year wedding anniversary. They both agreed to go to their favorite coffee shop for a quick date, after all, both of them have grown very busy with each other's business they couldn't find time for each other. As agreed, Peter went to the coffee shop. He even went an hour earlier with plans of surprising his beloved wife. He believes that his wife deserves to be treated extra special that day. Their agreement was five o'clock, so he went at 4, prepared a cake, a set of heart-shaped balloons, and a letter that says, “Happy Tenth Year, my love.”

Peter waited patiently, five o'clock came abruptly, but there was no sign of Riley. He said he'd wait for ten minutes, maybe she's just caught up in traffic. But she still did not come even when the clock struck 6:30. Peter did not lose his hope, he was willing to give his wife a chance, so he called her, but her phone just kept on ringing. It was then that he gave up, and went home, only to find out that his wife was there all along, sleeping cozily in bed. “How could she forget our agreement?” he said as he felt the sickening pain down his spine.

Now both of them were upset with each other. They were both in pain, but they were both unaware. None of the tried to communicate. Then, Peter started drinking almost every night. Riley wanted to confront him but she just can't. This same setting went on and on and on. Until Peter decided, he's already sick and tired of it. He wants divorce. So, he went to his lawyer, and came home that day with the divorce papers. But when he arrived home, Riley was no where to be found. He searched for her all around the house but her wife wasn't there. “Did she run away?” he asked himself, trembling. He went to Riley's closet; all her belongings are intact. Where could she be?

Down the streets of Maligaya, barangay Mambugan in Antipolo City, Riley was seen by Night High School students, walking blankly on the road, barefooted, and in a night gown.

“A ghost!” one student shouted. They almost ran frantically. Gladly, they did not. Instead, they approached her and immediately helped her. They sent her to a nearby hospital.

Early in the morning, Peter went to the police to report her missing wife. It was only then that he found out that her wife was in the hospital, cognitively impaired. There, he also found out that his wife has been diagnosed with young-onset dementia. What broke his heart even more is the fact that diagnosis came out on the day of their anniversary.

Only then was he able to grasp the situation. On the day of their anniversary, Riley had an appointment with her doctor informing her of her diagnosis. She was so devastated, she couldn't afford to face her husband, thinking, she will soon forget everything because of her illness. So, instead of showing up to their anniversary date, she just went home and cried herself out, until she was too weak to even speak. That night, she knew Peter had arrived but she pretended she was sleeping because her heart was broken.

Peter cried so hard until his tears refused from falling. If only he talked to her that night. If only he showed how angry and upset he felt, it would've led them to a conversation. They would've talked about the diagnosis. He would've comforted his wife. He wouldn't have come to the idea of asking for divorce.

With all that had happened, and everything falling to its place, Peter tossed away the idea of divorce and brought his wife home. He personally took care of her while witnessing as her health is slowly deteriorating. One night, Peter went to God in prayer, saying, “Lord, I know this is Your will, I do not have the right to question you. However, I wanted to ask a favor, please, Lord, grant my wife her good health the second time. Neither of us is perfect Lord, but we love you. Forgive me for wasting my time on alcohol instead of going to You in prayer. With all my heart, I am asking you, Lord, please grant my request. Please allow me to take care of my wife and please grant her the gift of good health once more, Lord. I am claiming that you will do this miracle in three months. Lord, grant us these three months.”

With fervent prayer, and strong faith, Peter took everything in his shoulders, this time, he trusted that God is with him. Even though Riley had a hard time communicating, Peter was too quick to determine patterns in her actions. He established routines to make Riley familiar with day-to-day activities. He filled the house with post its, telling her what she needs to do from the moment she opens her eyes until sundown when it is time for her to go to bed. Small cues like humming and singing have also been part of their routine. When Riley hums “Twinkle-Twinkle Little Star”, that means she's sleepy. When she sings it, that means she wants to play.

Peter, who once thought that he and his wife have already fallen out of love has realized that there never was an instance that they felt that way, it was just all about the lack of communication between them. Peter knew within him that he had never lost his love for his wife, not even an inch.

One day, Riley's doctor informed him about a silver lining. Riley may be cured of her illness through a surgery. This surgery might be risky, but Peter's faith is greater than his fears. He bravely assigned Riley to the surgeon, paid an enormous sum of money, and gave God an even enormous amount of prayer. As soon as he saw Riley inside the room for surgery, Peter knelt down in prayer, asking God for the miracle.

Several hours passed, the surgeon went out, the surgery was successful, but it is likely that she will forget everything about the past, it may also be that she wouldn't remember even a single memory from her childhood. Despite this, Peter hoped for the best and held on tightly to faith.

After twelve long hours of sleep, Riley finally opened her eyes. Peter hugged her, crying. Peter asked her, “Baby, how do you feel?”

Riley did not answer.

He asked again, “Do you remember me?”

Then Riley said with tears in her eyes, "Yes babe. How could I ever forget you, my love, Peter."

Peter cried out in fullness of joy! Indeed, God granted them the miracle!

